

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to totally replace the fossil fuel consumption of certain needs in four European pilot farms, proving that fossil-free-energy farming is possible to be achieved with a sustainable way. Innovative Renewable Energy Sources (RES) technologies will be installed, tested, and evaluated, serving as the means of de-fossilizing evidence. The overall objective is to provide advanced, cost-effective, and sustainable technologies, that will offer operational flexibility, and superior thermal comfort of the animals for increased productivity with minimum climate change impact.

Introduction

Fossil fuel use in the agricultural domain has negative effects becoming a major source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with significant contributions to global climate change and the risk of food security (FAO, 2019; Dubois et al., 2017). One of the most energy consuming

sub-sectors of agriculture is intensive livestock that is mainly based on fossil fuels use. This sector includes more than 2.6 million farms spread all over the EU (EUROSTAT, 2018) - about 25% of all agricultural holdings - while it represents about 45% of the total energy demand (28 Mteo/year) in the agricultural sector (Dumont et al., 2017). Both electricity and thermal energy is required to cover its strongly diversified energy demand, such as cooling-heating of the indoor livestock buildings environment, running of equipment and tractors, lighting, and ventilation systems. However, more sustainable livestock production and de-fossilizing energy needs in husbandry facilities emerge as crucial aspects within EU. With declining costs and improvement of reliability and performance of key RES technologies, the opportunities for farmers and specifically for livestock producers to engage in RES production are increasing, and new business models are emerging on the market.

Overall Approach

To that end, RES4LIVE will adapt and test promising RES technologies in energy-intensive livestock farming for greatly reducing the fossil energy that is the main source to cover the energy demand. Dedicated, optimal designs combined with energy efficiency and other solutions are proposed, demonstrated in 4 pilot farms (Fig. 1), and evaluated technically, economically, environmentally, and socially. The overall objective is to provide advanced and cost-effective technologies to the livestock sector that ensure the sustainability of the farms' operation, and the superior thermal comfort of the animals for increased productivity with minimum climate change impact.

Fig. 1: RES4LIVE pilot farms' locations and hosted animals

The strategic objective of RES4LIVE is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective, and case-sensitive RES solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming, as shows its overall concept in Fig. 2 below.

Fig. 1: RES4LIVE overall concept

Pilot farms

RES4LIVE approach is based on “diversification” principle so that to cover different climatic conditions and animals’ species that differentiate the livestock practices. ILVO (Belgium) is a farrow-to-finish pig farm for research and educational purposes alongside a normal commercial production. Within RES4LIVE, modular heat pumps and PVT collectors will be installed. The overall outcome is the replacement of 220,000 kWh/year with renewable energy plus electricity demand. In the commercial farm GOLINELLI (Italy), a heat pump and PVT system will be installed for the nursery barn, and thermal insulation will be added in the hog barn. The project will lead to the replacement of 100% of electricity and 100% of LPG consumption for the nursery barn with RES and efficiency measures, thus saving a total of 29,350 kg CO₂/year. LVAT (Germany) is a dairy farm containing a biogas plant which will be upgraded from biomethane production. A PVT system will be also installed for hot water and electricity generation, and a retrofitted tractor for biomethane use and an electrical driven

tractor will be demonstrated. The above interventions are expected to lead to CO₂ emissions' reduction of around 99,000 kg/year. Moreover, the CO₂ savings from the fuel for transport are estimated to 73,400 kg/year, almost equally shared between the biomethane tractor and an e-tractor. At last, in the experimental poultry farm located in the AUA campus, a heat pump, standard PV panels, LED lights and inverter-driven motors of the ventilators will be installed to replace by 100% the whole electricity consumption, leading to CO₂-eq. savings of 5,100 kg/year.

Scientific and technology development activities

After thorough market research, and consultation with the German pilot farm and manufacturers, the design and manufacturing of the small-scale biogas to biomethane upgrading plant, equipped with filling station, has been completed. Based on the required fuel autonomy of the farm's tractor, all the necessary engine modifications and retrofitting have been completed to ensure its smooth operation on biomethane. A series of modular heat pumps have been designed from swine and poultry farms, based on the required needs and indoor environmental conditions for each pilot farm. A standardised solution for roof-mounted PVT systems for livestock applications has been also developed for the swine and cattle pilot farms. The manufacturing process of both solutions has already been started, with preparatory installation works ongoing. An overview of the main adapted technologies is given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Overview of the main adapted technologies

Furthermore, an inventory of renewable energy sources, and energy efficiency technologies was also realized, containing information about renewable energy sources, and energy efficiency measures. Additionally, a numerical simulation model was developed, where the most promising technologies were combined and evaluated in terms of energetic

performance GHG emissions and cost. Reports on both activities are publicly available in the project’s website¹.

Optimal design with control, implementation, and pilot testing

To fully satisfy the energy demand in livestock buildings, optimisation of energy generation technologies is vital for energy systems efficient operation and cost effectiveness. Following the analysis of energy demand/ consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms (Fig.4 - The report can be found in the project’s website), a farm-specific numerical platform of open architecture capable to simulate and optimise integrated RES energy systems, as well as smart control modules capable to optimally match the energy supply and demand sides, having in the spotlight the conservation of indoor climate conditions within the thermal comfort zone, were developed.

Fig. 4: Energy, gas, and fuel consumption in ILVO swine farm

Furthermore, the effect of thermal comfort to the productivity of the specific animals under investigation has been also examined to be used as input in the above. At the same time the integrated designs of the energy systems, according to the consumption profiles of each pilot farm and the availability of RES, has progressed significantly, while the preparatory works are on-going. As final step, data collection has been initiated, in order to for them to be processed, and analysed for the overall approach’s multi-level assessment and validation in technical, economic, and environmental, and social level.

¹ www.res4live.eu

Activities for impact generation

To effectively address this worldwide challenge in the areas of agriculture and fossil fuel use reduction, AREA ZERO (“Alliance for Renewable Energy in Agriculture and Zero Fossil Energy”), as well as for supporting the extraction of policy recommendations and best practices adoption, among others. End-users and other stakeholders have been approached through workshops and questionnaires, considering their views/needs and approaches in the development process, as part of the co-design work. The first set of practice abstracts, containing innovative knowledge and recommendation for their daily practice, can be found in the project’s website. The efforts to identify lock-ins and barriers towards the fossil fuel free energy transition at regional, national, and European level, has been also initiated in collaboration with the abovementioned stakeholders.

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